

SUSTAINABILITY OF SOCIAL POLICIES IN THE ERA OF PRESIDENT SOEHARTO TO PRESIDENT JOKOWI DODO (POVERTY ALLEVIATION POLICY CASE STUDY)

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Abstract

The government continues to make efforts in the context of the welfare of its people, one of the efforts taken is through the establishment of policies. In the era of President Soeharto until the current era of President Jokowi Dodo, there is one policy that is still relevant today, namely the poverty alleviation policy. Poverty is a timeless problem even in developed countries. This study aims to determine the sustainability of social policies in the era of President Soeharto to President Jokowi Dodo. This study uses qualitative research methods, while the data collection techniques are carried out by exploring journals, books and other relevant information. After the data is collected, then the data is analyzed and presented descriptively. The results of the study indicate that the sustainability of poverty alleviation social policies from the era of President Soeharto through the strategy of meeting the basic needs of the people as stated in the Eight-Year National Development Plan (Penasbede). The sustainability of this poverty alleviation social policy was continued until the era of President Jokowi through community empowerment as well as the provision of social assistance.

Keywords: Social Policy, Era of President Soeharto, Era of President Jokowi Dodo

INTRODUCTION

The government continues to make efforts in order to prosper its people, one of the efforts taken is through the establishment of policies. In the era of president Soeharto to the era of President Jokowi Dodo now, there is one policy that is still relevant today, namely social policies regarding poverty alleviation. According to Nitto, social policy is any action taken by the government that can affect the welfare of the community. The actions taken are not only focused on the fields of social work but also on other, broader areas of development. In other

words, the government is responsible for providing services to the poor; providing guarantees to the people so as not to fall into poverty; providing services to the entire community in improving the quality of life of the community; and issues related directly or indirectly to efforts to fulfill services carried out by the government (Fedryansyah, 2013). Poverty is a timeless problem in even developed countries. The problem of poverty has always received major attention in Indonesia. This happens because of the government's awareness that failure to overcome the problem of poverty will be able to cause the emergence of various social, economic, and political problems in the midst of society (Purwanto, 2007). Poverty can be grouped into two categories, namely absolute poverty and relative poverty. Absolute poverty refers to a consistent set of standards, unaffected by time and place/country. An example of an absolute measurement is the percentage of the population that eats below sufficient amounts sustaining the needs of the human body (roughly 2000-2500 calories per day for adult males) (Setiono & Srientini, 2014).

The Economic Crisis of 1998 dealt a major blow to the national economy, including the increasing number of people's poverty which rose to 49.50 million or about 24.23% of the total population of Indonesia, from only 34.01 million (17.47%) in 1996. To reduce the poverty rate caused by the economic crisis, the government then established poverty reduction efforts as one of the priorities of the Indonesian government. The implementation of the poverty reduction program carried out since 1998 until now, in general, has been able to reduce Indonesia's poverty rate which amounted to 47.97 million or around 23.43% in 1999 to 30.02 million or around 12.49% in 2011. Based on the World fact book, BPS, and the World Bank, at the world level, the decline in the number of poor people in Indonesia is among the fastest compared to other countries. It was recorded that in the range from 2005 to 2009 Indonesia was able to reduce the average rate of decline in the number of poor people per year by 0.8%, much higher than the achievements of other countries such as Cambodia, Thailand, China, and Brazil which were only in the range of 0.1% per year (Tim Nasional Acceleration of Poverty in Indonesia, n.d.) . Therefore, this research has the aim of determining the sustainability of social policies in the era of president Soeharto to President Jokowi Dodo. Then, the discussion in this article is related to the program that has been set by the government and the Law to answer problems with relevance and tested validity.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses qualitative research methods. Qualitative research is research using a natural setting with the intention of interpreting a phenomenon that occurs and is carried out by involving various existing methods. Qualitative research aims to find and describe narratively the activities carried out and the impact of the actions carried out on their lives (Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, 1994). Meanwhile, the data collection technique is carried out by exploring journals, books and other relevant information. The journals used are searched for in the Google Scholar search with several writing formats, after the data is collected, then the data is analyzed and presented descriptively.

DISCUSSION

Social Policy

Social policy is a form of public policy. Social policy is a government decree made to respond to issues of a public nature, namely overcoming social problems or meeting the needs of many people (Bessant, Judith, Rob Watts, 2006). Related to that, social policy is a policy that concerns society as a whole which concerns various aspects, both social, political, and economic aspects. Economic and political factors are an integral part (parts that cannot be separated from each other). The ultimate goal of social policy is social welfare. Social welfare is a condition (state of well-being), to achieve human well-being must meet its needs both material and non-material (Nature, 2009). Although the social policy, which became a guideline in the preparation of the program, has been well designed, it does not mean that its implementation will be in accordance with the expected objectives. In other words, the success of a policy is seen from how the policy can be interpreted by the relevant parties. Especially, how a policy is interpreted into a more applicable guideline to be a guide in the implementation of the policy (Fedryansyah, 2013).

Poverty Alleviation Policy Analysis in Indonesia

The government improved the coordination of poverty reduction, the government issued Presidential Regulation Number 15 of 2010, concerning the Acceleration of Poverty Reduction which is an improvement of Presidential Regulation Number 13 of 2009 concerning Coordination of Poverty Reduction. In the Presidential Regulation, it is mandated to form a National Team for the Acceleration of Poverty Reduction (TNP2K) at the central level whose membership consists of elements of the government, society, the business world, and other stakeholders. Meanwhile, in the provinces and regencies/cities, a Provincial and Regency/City Poverty Reduction Coordination Team (TKPK) was formed (Ministry of Informatics and Communication, 2011). The government currently has a variety of integrated poverty reduction programs ranging from social assistance-based poverty reduction programs, community empowerment-based poverty reduction programs and poverty reduction programs based on small business empowerment, which are run by various elements of the Government both central and regional (National Team for Poverty Acceleration in Indonesia, n.d.) . The strategy to combat poverty proposed by Gunnar Adler Karlsson quoted by Andre Bayo Ala (1981) includes: (1) a strategy in the short term, namely transferring resources to the poor in sufficient quantities. Improving the state of poverty in the short term includes creating job opportunities, increasing incomes, and improving its distribution; (2) Long-term strategy by growing local self-help (Hidayah, 2022). Improvement in the long run by improving and fulfilling the dignity of living individually and socially. Meanwhile, the World Bank stated that every decade the poverty alleviation strategy has developed from job creation, income generation, and health and education development, protection to the empowerment of the poor.

Table 1. Poverty Alleviation during the era of President Soeharto to Jokowi

No.	The Era of Leadership	Policy
1	President Suharto	Inpres of underdeveloped villages
		Poor welfare assistance program
		Independent young family program
		Women's role enhancement programs
		Cadet reef development and assistance to poor families
		Increased intensification of food crop agriculture
		Education and health programs
		Business development kecil-kredit candak kulak
		Transmigration program
		Family Welfare Savings (Takesra) and Family Welfare Business Credit (Kukesra)
2	President BJ Habibie	Social Rescue Network (JPS) Program
		Subsidized rice for the community
		Funds for the education of children from underprivileged and prosperous families
		Scholarships for underprivileged students
		Labor-intensive programs
3	President Gusdur	Health and education services for the poor
		Improvement of the residential environment
		Development of the business culture of the poor
		Clean water subsidies
		Compensation for fuel price increases in education, health, and public transportation services
4	President Megawati	Cheap electricity for poor households
		Subsidies for underprivileged communities
		Interest subsidy for microenterprise credit programs
		Fertilizer subsidies
		Service
5	President SBY	Independent Community Empowerment Program (PNPM)
		Family Hope Program (PKH)
		Rice subsidy for the poor (Raskin)
		Poor Student Assistance (BSM)
		Program Askeskin/Jamkesmas
		Direct Cash Transfer Program (BLT)
		Community Temporary Direct Assistance Program (BLSM)
6	President Jokowi	Smart Indonesia Program (PIP)
		Healthy Indonesia Program (PIS)
		Family Hope Program (PKH)
		Prosperous Rice (Rastra) or Social Food Assistance
		Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT)
		Village Fund Program
		Agrarian Reform and Social Forestry Program (RAPS).

Source: (Situmorang, 2018)

The Poverty Alleviation Strategy implemented by the Government can be divided into two major parts, firstly protecting families and groups of people experiencing temporary poverty,

and secondly helping people experiencing chronic poverty by empowering and preventing new poverty. The strategy is further outlined in three programs that are directly directed at the poor, namely: (1) provision of basic needs; 2) the development of a social security system; and 3) development of business culture. In addition, the poor have their own strategies to overcome their poverty. The strategy taken is to borrow from informal institutions, increase working hours, family members join work, wander or save money (Yulianto, n.d.) .

The policy concepts used by the government in poverty alleviation programs can be distinguished based on tradition and the planning approach that underlies them. The tradition of planning according to John Friedmann consists of at least four types, namely: (1) planning as a social reform, that the state compiles and plans various development directives and guidelines for the community to follow and implement; (2) planning as a policy analysis, that policy makers (the government and other related parties) based on scientific data analysis compile and plan various development directions and guidelines that can be accepted and implemented by the community; (3) planning as social learning, that planning knowledge is obtained through experience and perfected through practice (learning by doing), planning and implementation of development are carried out together with the community with guidance from experts; and (4) planning as a social mobilization , that development planning must be carried out by the community and driven by various concepts / ideologies that have been embedded in their souls and cultures (Mustakim, 2021). Meanwhile, the types of poverty alleviation programs implemented by the government can be seen based on the development model underlying these programs to see the emphasis of the strategy implemented by the program. The development model adopted by developing countries is broadly divided into four development models. Development model I focuses on national income growth. Development model II focuses on equality and fulfillment of basic needs. Development model III seeks to improve the quality of human resources through the participation of the community and target groups in determining needs and participation in the development process. Meanwhile, the IV development model focuses on increasing competitiveness to face the era of globalization and the era of regional autonomy (Yulianto, n.d.) .

Sustainability of Poverty Alleviation Policies in Indonesia

The poverty reduction program in Indonesia has been implemented by the government since the old order precisely since the 1960s through a strategy to meet the basic needs of the people as stated in the Eight-Year National Development Plan (Penasbede). Based on the TAP MPRS No. II / MPRS / 1960 concerning the Outlines of the National Development Pattern of the Universe Planning the First Phase 1961-1969, the development pattern at that time was more aimed at realizing the welfare of the people equally. Development at that time was oriented towards increasing national income which formed the prosperity of the Indonesian people (Bureau of State Design, 1956). Prosperity is realized through various policies that will increase income independently. The fields of education, housing, and health, are getting special attention from the government. Then continued the policy to increase national and family income. The complete population quality improvement program is contained in the document National Development Planning Eight Years (Penasbede, 1961-1969) (Murdiyana & Mulyana,

2017). Comprehensive poverty reduction requires the involvement of various stakeholders. The central government, local governments, the business world (self-help sector) and the community are parties who have the same responsibility for poverty reduction. The government has implemented poverty reduction through various programs in an effort to adequately meet the basic needs of citizens, improve the socio-economic welfare of the poor, strengthen the socio-economic institutions of the community and carry out the acceleration of development of underdeveloped areas in an effort to achieve a prosperous, democratic and just Indonesian society. However, all these efforts have not been maximized without the support of other stakeholders. To support comprehensive poverty reduction and realize the acceleration of poverty reduction, four main strategies are formulated. During the leadership of Jokowi Jusuf Kalla, the government established these poverty reduction strategies including: (1) Improving social protection programs; (2) Improve access to basic services; (3) Empowerment of poor people; and (4) Creating inclusive development (Murdiyana & Mulyana, 2017). Keberelantan keb ijakanpemerintah regarding the poverty alleviation strategy in Indonesia is going quite well. This is marked by the government's efforts to issue several policies that are poured into laws and regulations which then formulate poverty alleviation programs. Starting from the old order period to the reigns of President Joko Widodo and Jusuf Kalla, they continue to strive to reduce the number of Indonesians living below the poverty line. Meanwhile, during the Jokowi-Ma'ruf Amin administration, Indonesian resident Joko Widodo (Jokowi) targets extreme poverty in Indonesia at zero percent by 2024. Vice President Ma'ruf Amin stated that poverty cannot be solved if it only relies on the provision of social assistance (bansos), in eradicating poverty in the country, it is necessary to go through two efforts, namely community empowerment as well as the provision of social assistance. This is evidenced by the decrease in the poverty rate by 0.17 percent from the conditions in September 2021, namely 26.5 million people or 9.71 percent of the poor population. There was a downward trend from the highest point in September 2020, namely 27.55 million people or 10.19 percent (Pratama, 2022).

CONCLUSION

The government continues to make efforts in order to prosper its people, one of the efforts taken is through the establishment of policies. In the era of president Soeharto to the era of President Jokowi Dodo now, there is one policy that is still relevant today, namely social policies regarding poverty alleviation. In the Soeharto era, the government made efforts to alleviate poverty through a strategy to meet the basic needs of the people as stated in the Eight-Year National Development Plan (Penasbede). Based on the TAP MPRS No. II / MPRS / 1960 concerning the Outlines of the National Development Pattern of the Universe Planning the First Phase 1961-1969, the development pattern at that time was more aimed at realizing the welfare of the people equally. The sustainability of this social policy of poverty alleviation was continued until the era of President Jokowi through community empowerment as well as the provision of social assistance. This is evidenced by the decrease in the poverty rate by 0.17 percent from the conditions in September 2021, namely 26.5 million people or 9.71 percent of the poor population. There was a downward trend from the highest point in September 2020, which was 27.55 million people or 10.19 percent.

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